

Abstracts from LU Open Science Days 2024

Crossing Boundaries with Open Science

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Building the Italian data stewards community

Andrea Tarallo¹, Giulia Caldoni², Roberta Ferretti³, Mauro Paschetta⁴ and Valentina Pasquale⁵

¹ National Research Council of Italy (CNR), Institute of Research on Terrestrial Ecosystems (IRET), Lecce, Italy

² Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna, Bologna, Italy.

³ National Research Council of Italy (CNR), Institute of Marine Engineering (INM), Genoa, Italy.

⁴ Politecnico di Torino, Turin, Italy.

⁵ Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Genoa, Italy

While the concepts of Open Science and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data are widely discussed in the research landscape, there is still limited focus on who actually supports and drives these processes. The data stewards play a critical role in ensuring the success of these initiatives, providing the necessary expertise and support for managing research data effectively and sustainably.

The Italian data stewards community was established in 2023 as a bottom-up initiative supported by the ICDI Competence Center and the European project Skills4EOSC. The community was created to identify and leverage the existing expertise in Italy, which, although present, remains fragmented and lacks a clear professional definition.

One of the community's initial efforts was to assess the existing data stewardship competencies and gaps related to data management practices in Italy.

This initial assessment revealed both strengths and areas for improvement, providing valuable insights for guiding future actions.

After one year, the community is evolving from a loose network into a more structured entity with a steering board, dedicated working groups and a manifesto outlining its key principles.

This community aims to foster collaboration among professionals in the field, particularly to address the following objectives:

1. To create opportunities for developing new, often unavailable, data stewardship competencies not typically offered through traditional educational programs.
2. To promote the convergence towards shared solutions in research data management.
3. To increase awareness and understanding of the Data Steward role both within and outside research institutions.

The ultimate goal of this initiative is to create a sustainable, supportive community that promotes the role of the Data Steward across Italy, ensuring that the essential work of supporting Open Science and FAIR data practices are recognised and strengthened within research institutions.

Acknowledgements:

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Reproducibility and the ReproducibiliTea Initiative

Jane Fisher¹

¹ Jane Fisher, AdvanSci Research Solutions, Lund, Sweden (jane.fisher@advansci-research.com)

Reproducibility and replicability are hallmarks of good science. Yet, a significant portion of published research in many scientific fields, including biomedicine, cannot be reproduced. As the scientific process continually evolves, a field known as metascience—dedicated to studying and improving the methods and practices of science itself—has emerged.

The ReproducibiliTea movement, launched at the University of Oxford in 2018, is a grassroots initiative that helps researchers create local Open Science journal clubs to discuss diverse issues, papers, and ideas to improve science. As part of this global effort, we have recently established a journal club in Lund to explore challenges in reproducibility within biomedicine and the wider scientific landscape. This presentation will introduce you to the ReproducibiliTea initiative and offer insight into the discussions happening at our journal club in Lund.

Exchanging Researcher Seats: Weaving Research with Indigenous Knowledges Systems for Forest-Fauna-Human management in the Colombian Amazon

Carlos Alberto Hernández-Vélez¹, in collaboration with CEIMA-Cachivera Vaupes Community, Airumakuchi Indigenous Amazonian Association and Torsten Krause²

¹ LUCSUS, Lund University, carlos.velez@lucsus.lu.se

² LUCSUS, Lund University, torsten.krause@lucsus.lu.se

A growing number of researchers and scientific institutions realize the importance to connect and complement western scientific knowledge with other forms of knowing. This turn towards epistemic pluralism requires researchers to engage in a collaborative and inclusive dialogue with the diversity of knowledge held by local and indigenous peoples and learn from it. Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) is of particular interest for our study on sustainable wildlife management in the Colombian Amazon region, which is based on a biocultural and social-ecological systems perspective. We aim to contribute to this process by describing and analysing the collective learning experiences and methodologies we use to integrate institutions, people, knowledges, and actions at various scales. Over a period of 4 years, we developed participatory research with two teams of local indigenous researchers and carried out monthly workshops with local researchers inspired by Participatory Action Research (PAR). These workshops focused on TEK and local wildlife uses in two indigenous communities where two groups of local researchers cocreated participatory workshops with us. Combined with an ethnographic approach for data collection, we present the categories, variables, and information of TEK about their territories describing local cartography and knowledge about 56 species of wildlife, including their use. We first discuss our transdisciplinary research method and its significance for documenting and strengthening local TEK. In addition, our findings also show major threats to TEK, such as institutional and legal challenges, the role of traditional knowledge holders who act as guardians of TEK, and the socio-cultural transformations across the Amazon region. We conclude with insights how research can support TEK and be leveraged for more inclusive conservation and a more respectful interaction and sustainable use of wildlife.

Science activism, citizen science, and partnership with society

Lydia Bucher¹

¹ iGEM Lund University

Synthetic biology holds vast potential for transformative applications, yet its complexity can make it challenging for the general public to approach. Our team seeks to bridge this gap by developing educational tools that present essential concepts in an engaging, accessible way. Through interactive workshops, participation in Kulturnatten, and social media outreach, we reached diverse audiences, sparking interest and facilitating dialogue around synthetic biology. A core focus of our workshops, particularly aimed at high school and middle school students, is to cultivate critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Additionally, we conducted an ethical discussion to prompt students to consider the societal implications of advancements in synthetic biology. These workshops engage students in hands-on activities that foster a well-rounded understanding. Additionally, we developed a synthetic biology-themed card game as an interactive learning tool. This game invites players to explore foundational principles and practical applications, making complex scientific ideas accessible and enjoyable. By combining direct engagement with innovative educational resources, our team aims to demystify synthetic biology, inspiring broader appreciation and thoughtful participation in this evolving field.

Sjölabbet – Creating avenues for environmental monitoring

Per Wilhelmsson¹

¹ PKI Utveckling AB

Our ability to understand the environment depends on our capacity to collect and analyse data. Our capacity to collect and analyse data depends on the accessibility of instruments and knowledge as well as on the amount of people engaged in these activities. Recent years advances in open-source hardware (through 3D printer technology) and open-source software have enabled for a paradigm shift in manufacturing and implementation of cost-effective scientific equipment, such as for microscopes through the OpenFlexure project (openflexure.org). The concepts of open science and open hardware are still somewhat unfamiliar in education and academia. This highlights that spreading awareness of these contemporary concepts, striving towards democratisation of science, is of high priority.

Being able to collect more image data of microorganisms can contribute to a better understanding of their temporal and spatial distribution, at a time when a rapidly changing climate pose an increasingly significant stress factor on our ecosystems.

Sjölabbet is a research-through-education initiative that promotes the use of the OpenFlexure microscope (OFM) in educational settings as a tool to contribute towards aquatic environmental monitoring. Sjölabbet emerged as a collaboration between Vattenhallen Science Center and a local company engaged in biological data collection (PKI Utveckling). Sjölabbet is currently helping teachers develop the skills to assemble their own OFMs as well as informing them on how to collect and share microorganism image data to relevant national environmental monitoring databases. The aim of Sjölabbet is to create avenues to contribute towards our understanding of the environment, bridging the gap between the environmentally interested and environmental research, by promoting the use of open science methodologies in education. This will raise more awareness of biodiversity research, open science and open hardware.

Maximizing Scientific Output through Data FAIRness

Fredrik Bolmsten and Massimiliano Novelli¹

¹ European Spallation Source ERIC, Data Management and Software Centre, Lyngby, Denmark (Max.Novelli@ess.eu)

The European Spallation Source (ESS) has set the ambitious goal to implement the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) to all scientific data acquired and produced under its umbrella. In this talk, we will discuss ESS approach to FAIR data management and its integration with the PaNOSC (Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud) data portal to support a collaborative and data-driven scientific ecosystem. The PaNOSC project, a European initiative to provide open data services to photon and neutron research infrastructures, offers through its data portal a central platform for the sharing and discovery of open data across facilities. It aims to become the central place for researchers to discover previous experiments and related data, and open data in general.

We will explore the strategies employed by ESS to ensure data FAIRness. They include understanding of the scientific domain, familiarity with the acquisition technologies, tight collaborations with stakeholders, robust metadata standards, automated data capture, and adherence to open data policies, which allow for seamless data integration with the PaNOSC portal, and potentially with other data services. We will also discuss the role of the PaNOSC data portal, and similar initiatives, in enhancing data discoverability and scientific output.

Attendees will gain insights into how to leverage multiple strategies to foster an open-science environment and enable international cross-facility data sharing that supports scientific advancement. This talk will be valuable for researchers, data managers and IT professionals interested in adopting FAIR principles within their projects and exploring practical applications of open science data platforms.

Researchdata.se – Your gateway to Swedish research data

Arin Tham¹

¹ Swedish National Data Service (SND)

Three years ago, the Swedish National Data Service (SND) initiated discussions for launching a new national portal for accessing, sharing, and managing data created by researchers based at universities and other research institutions in Sweden. These vivid discussions emerged against the backdrop of a rather diffuse landscape of databases, catalogues, and digital archives. The question that emerged was, what can be done to strengthen findability to Swedish research data nation-wide? In an attempt to answer this, SND put forward the idea that a new, national web portal be created. Its primary goals were to develop a coherent search on a wider platform, to enable interoperability between Swedish actors, to promote transdisciplinary studies, to make greater use of collected Swedish knowledge and experiences, and to offer tools and services from SND and other national actors in a coordinated fashion.

SND, thus, proceeded to form a new project group with expertise in research data management that rapidly began working on this ambitious plan.

The project work for the new portal has focused on how to design the portal in a way that is clear, communicative and efficient. Additionally, there have also been several discussions on ways to share data (mainly entry points), besides SND's own data publication platform. A key focus has also been discussing the right conditions for harvesting metadata and cooperating with national partners in this regard. Furthermore, we have been keen to contribute to creating training resources, learning materials, and other relevant material for open access know-how. However, we have been careful not to reinvent the wheel but to emphasise and expand national collaboration with regards to education/training. This and much more work is yet to be done, ahead of the launch and after. SND has a bold and committed plan for the launch of the www.researchdata.se portal, which together with national partners, is planned for February 2025.

The poster presented at the LU Open Science Days will show the thought process behind the project, including its purpose and aims, but also the method of work and challenges faced, along with identifying project partners and their roles, and finally offer some conclusions.

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SND – a national contributor to open science and Skills 4EOSC project partner

William Gothlin Illsley ¹

¹ Swedish National Data Service (SND)

The Swedish National Data Service has for the last two years, been an active participant in the Skills4EOSC (Skills for the European Open Science commons) project. This project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI, is focused on the creation of a training ecosystem for Open and FAIR science. Along with the proposal of minimum viable skillsets, curricula, and methodologies for developing routine and enduring pathways to open science, one of the ultimate goals of the Skills4EOSC project is to establish a network of competence centres. There, the project's members will serve as a digital platform for knowledge exchange, which creates better conditions for implementing and delivering the training materials to target audiences ranging from researchers to policy makers. As a project member and national node for Sweden, the Swedish National Data Service will act as a competence centre for the Skills4EOSC project following the launch of the competence centre network on June 24th, 2024.

This poster will briefly discuss SND's role as a national research infrastructure, such as the tools we have in place for following FAIR data principles, describing, sharing, finding and re-using data, as well as further elaborating our role in the Skills4EOSC project and its implications for the SND network and open science in Sweden.

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HOMEROS - Harmonising Observations from Multi-hazard Environments in Research for Open Science - Expectations and first examples from the EOSC EU Node services for Researchers

Angeliki Adamaki¹ in collaboration with Angelos Zymvragakis² Ioannis Spingos² and Vassilis Anagnostou³

¹ Angeliki Adamaki, Lund University, Sweden, angeliki.adamaki@nateko.lu.se

² National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece

³ Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

The HOMEROS project focuses on enhancing multi-hazard assessments, particularly for earthquakes, floods, and landslides in high-risk areas in Greece. It aims to harmonize and standardize observational data across seismology, geodesy, and geology using Open Science frameworks. By integrating pan-European and local resources, HOMEROS supports robust hazard assessments, fosters interdisciplinary collaboration, and emphasizes accessible data sharing to improve disaster preparedness and resilience.

The poster presented at the LU Open Science Days 2024 showcases preliminary results from tests on the (recently launched) EOSC EU Node, focusing on tools and services that facilitate data interoperability, visualization, and analytical capabilities tailored to researchers' needs. These early examples, resulting from collaboration among Lund University, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and National Kapodistrian University of Athens, underscore the EOSC potential to streamline data sharing across disciplines, offering virtual environments that address challenges in data access and integration. Future steps will involve expanding these services to further support cross-disciplinary collaboration and enhance Europe's Open Science infrastructure.

Engaging minds, engaging objects – a hands on session on object based learning

Karin Annebäck¹ and Frida Stenmark¹

¹ Museum of artistic process and public art, Lund University

Skissernas Museum – Museum of Artistic Process and Public Art – is part of Lund University and constitutes a platform for interdisciplinary collaborations across borders. In a breathtaking environment the museum forms a place where art helps us think and develop new ideas as well as teaching methods.

In recent years, Skissernas Museum has begun using the collection to develop and establish a new pedagogical method that promotes higher education pedagogical development, student-centered learning, and interdisciplinary collaborations. The method is called object-based learning (OBL). It involves students working closely and intensively with physical objects, art in our case, stimulating deep learning and raising subject-relevant questions.

The goal is to create an inclusive and student-centered method with an interdisciplinary approach. The method is based on dialogue between students, teachers, and Museum staff, where the students' curiosity leads them towards active knowledge production.

The method can be applied in a wide range of disciplines. At the moment we do object-based learning sessions with students and staff from the Faculty of Law, the Faculty of Social Sciences and the Faculty of Humanities. But we are keen to reach out further. Rather than a traditional poster session the museum educators will an object to the table. Let's start talking!

Accelerating Teaching: Using the stories from accelerator-driven Large-Scale Research Infrastructures to inspire high school teachers, through a Massive Open Online Course for European educator professional development

Joanna Lewis¹, Monica Almqvist² and Heidi LaGrasta³

¹ European Spallation Source ERIC, Lund, Sweden

² Department of Biomedical Engineering and Vattenhallen Science Center, Lund University

³ MAX IV

In 2022-2024 European Spallation Source (ESS) and Lund University were part of a collaboration that put together a Massive Open Online Course, or MOOC, for European high school science teachers. With EU ERASMUS+ funding, the MOOC aimed to “Inspire teachers to use the stories from large facilities across Europe to teach the topics they all teach, such as: Forces, Magnetism, the structure of an atom, light, electromagnetism and more.”

The consortium consisted of three Research Infrastructures (ESS, MAX IV and CERN), together with the science teacher training departments from the universities in Lund, Malmö and Copenhagen, as well as two science centres - Lund University’s Vattenhallen and Experimentarium in Denmark. European Schoolnet – a Brussels-based institution who produce MOOCs aimed at teachers, contributed by hosting the MOOC on their science teacher network, Scientix.

The MOOC objectives were for participants to:

- Understand the value of large facilities like CERN in providing a context for STEM teaching
- Learn how to engage students in modern science research through free digital tools
- Gain a well-rounded understanding of how particle accelerators work, are used in society and how they contribute to modern research in all STEM subjects
- Identify and build on educational methodologies that stimulate students’ analytical and critical thinking skills, collaboration, communication, and active participation competencies.

The course ran for two months and reached 1300 teachers from 23 different countries. After the time-specific element was over (which included weekly live webinars), it continues in legacy format on the Scientix website with all the materials still available to access or download.

This poster will show the aims and outcomes of the project, visualise some of the Learning Scenarios (extended cross-curricular lesson plans) that were developed, and highlight future plans, as the project draws to a close in November 2024.

https://bit.ly/AT_MOOC23

<https://www.scientix.eu/accelerating-teaching-mooc>

Fossil hunting and climate labs for children and young people

Jutta Holst¹, Johan Gren² and Monica Almqvist³

¹ ICOS Sweden and Department of Physical Geography and Ecosystem Science, Lund University

² Vattenhallen Science Center, Lund University

³ Department of Biomedical Engineering and Vattenhallen Science Center, Lund University

Vattenhallen Science Center collaborates with researchers in almost all development of new exhibitions and activities. Vattenhallen's most important purposes are to work for broadened recruitment and to be an outreach arena for Lund University's researchers. At our stand in the poster session, you will meet PhD Johan Gren, paleontologist and deputy director at Vattenhallen, who, together with a designer and a communicator, has developed an activity where children can dig for 3D-printed dinosaur fossils. Jutta Holst, researcher and director of ICOS Sweden, will show a couple of climate laboratory exercises for school students in Vattenhallen and also talk about the Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS) and how they contribute with measurement data for monitoring greenhouse gas levels in the atmosphere in Europe.